

SHORT NOTES

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE ESSENTIAL OIL FROM SEEDS OF *DESCURAINIA SOPHIA* (LINN), WEBLE EX-PRANTL, SYN. *SISYMBRIUM* *SOPHIA* (LINN)

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The plant of *Descurainia sophia* (Linn) belongs to the Family Cruciferae and is distributed widely in temperate Himalayas from Kashmir to Kumaon. The seeds of the plant are bitter, expectorant, restorative, tonic and useful in fevers, bronchitis and dysentery. According to the indigenous system of medicine these seeds are efficacious for worms and calculous complaints. The seeds are also used as a substitute or adulterant of the seeds of *Sisymbrium irio* (Linn) (Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Vol. I, p. 150).

The fatty oil from the seeds has already been examined and the presence of linolenic, linoleic, oleic, erucic, palmitic and stearic acids reported (Baslas, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1959, **22**, 122). On steam-distillation of the seeds a foul smelling essential oil was obtained in 0.025% yield.

The oil (200 c.c.) was fractionated in Tower's microfractionating column when the following fractions were obtained :

(I) 119-22° (1.5 c.c.), (II) 151-52° (3 c.c.), (III) 198-200° (2.5 c.c.), (IV) 242-44° (12 c.c.); (V), residue (1 c.c.).

Fraction (IV) forms the chief component, and possesses the following properties which resemble closely with those of benzyl isothiocyanate, as shown in Table I.

Fractions (I) and (II) were identified as allyl cyanide and allyl isothiocyanate respectively. Presence of allyl disulphide was suspected in fraction (III), but no confirmation was obtained for the same. Similarly the presence of propenyl isothiocyanate has been indicated in the residue, but it could not be confirmed.

Isolation of the Oil.—The essential oil was obtained by steam-distillation of the dry seeds from a copper still provided with a copper condenser and extracting the steam distillate with petroleum ether. After removal of the solvent a greenish yellow oil was obtained possessing the following properties : d_{15}^{15} 1.044; n_D^{15} 1.5278; $[\alpha]_D^{20} \pm 0$; acid value 23.6 ; ester value 43.

Fractionation.—The oil (20 c.c.) was fractionated in Tower's microfractionating apparatus consisting of a boiling flask (50 c.c.) attached with a standard joint tubulature and a Vigreux column with attached condenser and ground-glass receiver. Careful fractionation yielded five fractions (*vide supra*).

Identification of the Fractions.—Fraction (I) possesses the following properties : d_{15}^{15} 0.8367; n_D^{15} 1.048; saponification number 48.2. (Found : C, 71.2; H, 7.5; N, 21.3. Calc. for C_4H_5N : C, 71.64; H, 7.46; N, 20.9%). It was suspected to be allyl cyanide which was confirmed by hydrolysis with alcoholic potash when crotonic acid (m.p. 72°) was obtained.

Fraction (II) was strongly pungent and lachrymatory. (Found: N, 13.9; S, 32.1. Calc. for C_3H_5NCS : N, 14.1; S, 32.3%). It was identified as allyl thiocyanate by preparing a semicarbazide, m.p. 195-96° (Rosenthaler, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1927, 265, 113) and allylthiourea, m.p. 74-76° (Tornoe, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1288).

Semicarbazide was prepared in the usual way by treating a few drops of the fraction in ethanol with semicarbazide hydrochloride, when a crystalline solid separated after 24 hours.

Allylthiourea was obtained by warming a mixture of 0.5 c.c. of the fraction and excess of ammonia and cooling it subsequently. Confirmation was obtained by mixed m.p. with a genuine sample, when no depression was found.

Fraction (III) strongly smelt like garlic and was suspected to be allyl disulphide. But no solid derivative was obtained excepting a precipitate with silver nitrate solution in alcohol. (Found: S, 43.2. Calc. for $C_6H_{10}S_2$: S, 43.8%).

Fraction (IV) distilled at 138-39°/20 mm and possessed the properties mentioned in Table I. It was identified as benzyl isothiocyanate by preparing its thiourea derivative and phenylbenzylthiosemicarbazide. (Found: C, 64.5; H, 4.9; N, 9.9; S, 21.45. Calc. for C_8H_7NS : C, 64.4; H, 4.6; N, 9.6; S, 21.4%).

TABLE I

Properties.	Fraction IV.	Benzyl isothiocyanate.
B.P.	242-44°	243° (<i>Ber.</i> , 1868, 1, 201)
n_D^{15}	1.6044	1.6049 (<i>J. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1906, 89, 564)
Thiourea m.p.	162-64°	164° (Salkovsky, <i>Ber.</i> , 1891, 24, 2724)
Thiosemicarbazide m.p.	156-57°	158° (Blanksma, <i>Pharm. Weekblad.</i> , 1914, 51, 138; <i>Chem. Zentr.</i> , 1915, 1, 262).

Fraction (V), the residue, appears to contain propenyl isothiocyanate. (Found: C, 48.5; H, 5.5; N, 13.9; S, 32.1. Calc. for C_4H_5NS : C, 48.48; H, 5.1; N, 14.1; S, 32.3%). No solid derivative could be obtained to confirm the above conclusion based on the consideration of the composition mentioned above. From the amount of various fractions the approximate composition of the oil is as follows: Benzyl isothiocyanate 60%, allyl isothiocyanate 15%, allyl disulphide 12.5, allyl cyanide 7.5% and propenyl isothiocyanate (?), 5%.

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